

CHANGING TRENDS IN US POLICY TOWARDS THE KASHMIR ISSUE: AN ANALYSIS OF GEORGE BUSH ERA (1988-1991)

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Abstract

This article analyzes the changing contours of U.S. policy on the Kashmir dispute, focusing particularly on the George H. W. Bush period (1988–1991). Starting with a historical introduction to American involvement in the Kashmir conflict since 1947, it places the policy changes in perspective against the background of the Indian-held Jammu and Kashmir uprising in 1989.

The article examines the changing American position under the Bush administration, marking a hesitant but significant departure from Cold War alignments. Particular attention is devoted to Pakistan's contribution to internationalizing the conflict and the initial U.S. reaction, which was indicative of increasing concern regarding regional instability. The 1990 Indo-Pak crisis, triggered by military mobilizations and escalation fears, is examined as a turning point. The article also addresses the new U.S. view of Kashmir in terms of nuclear non-proliferation, the start of a strategic connection between the Kashmir dispute and a nuclear Pakistan.

INTRODUCTION

The patterns of international politics changed more rapidly during the 20th century than the previous ones. World War I (1914 -1918) marked the end of Europe as a point around which the international system revolved for about 400 years (Palit, 2001). The twenty years period between the two World Wars saw the emergence of new centers of international power and at the same time new dimensions of international conflicts. The Post World War II (1939-1945) era was marked by an intense confrontation between East and West. International relations developed into a pattern dubbed as 'cold war'. However, even as the pattern of international politics was being reshaped new conditions and relationship were coming up to the chessboard of power politics (Stylianou, Buchan, & Dunn, 2015). In another 20 years, the international

system was transformed from a simplified bipolar world into a highly pluralistic one, characterized by an extremely complex set of relationships involving all the countries of the world. This rapidly changing pattern of international politics made the conduct of foreign policy a difficult job. This is particularly true for a country like the United States, which has been so extensively involved in the internal affairs of other countries in the world. Kashmir is a regional conflict, which now has attained the degree of intensity at international level. As in the case of other regional conflicts, the American foreign policy has allegedly influenced in the cause of events in Kashmir.

The purpose of this study is to analyze the attitude of the United States towards Kashmir

dispute. The conflict has historical and political significance in the sense that Kashmir is the focal point in Pakistan's security perception and the Indo-Pak dispute over it has bedeviled American relations with both countries. Being a permanent member of the Security Council, the role of United States over the Kashmir dispute has been no less significant. This role was rather complicated because of the growing complexity of world affairs enmeshed in the politics of the cold war. Mr. Noel Baker, the British representative in the UN in 1948 described the Kashmir issue as "The greatest and the gravest single issue in those affairs". Even today, it remains greatest and gravest single issues in South Asia, if not in the world (Clad, 2020). The aim of the study is to examine the Kashmir dispute and the role of United States during **George Bush Era (1988-1991)**.

American Policy on Kashmir: A Historical Survey

A host of regional interests in south Asia have played a fundamental role in shaping the US viewpoint and policy vis-a-vis the Kashmir conflict. Changing circumstances have given birth to new US perspectives, which have often been at variance with each other. American viewpoints on Kashmir have been consistent on their inconsistency (Palit, 2001).

Initially in 1947, US was reluctant to get involved in the contention and avoided supporting either India or Pakistan. But the evolving cold war with the Soviet Union in Iran, Turkey and West Asia forced it to review the significance of South Asia (Palit, 2001). Dennis Kux writes in his book "The United States and Pakistan, 1947-2000: Disenchanted Allies", that "In February 1947, Britain informed America of its decision to grant India Independence. In 1948, financially strapped London also informed Washington that it could no longer help Greece and Turkey against communist threat. So, the President Harry S. Truman decided that the "United States would take up the burden". Three months later, on June 5, 1947, Secretary of State Marshall announced another key policy initiative; United States

willingness to help European economic recovery. In the summer of 1949, Washington also showed interest in events in the Middle East. At that time civil war was raging in China where United States supported Nationalists. Washington was content to let the British worry about the emerging States of India and Pakistan. Kux writes:

The principal anxiety was that continuing Hindu Muslim differences might spark even more intense violence and lead to broader political instability in Asia. The United States simply did not perceive major interests in the sub-continent. This can also be explained in the fact that the region stood apart from the cold war struggle between the Soviet Union and the United States and both did not feel any urgency to establish friendly ties with either country. India, however, proved sharper and quicker and built-up friendly ties with Moscow. On the other hand, the foreign policy of Pakistan during the initial years of its inception was not tilted to any block, showing a neutral and balanced attitude towards the Soviet Union. However, given the creeping sense of insecurity from the Indian side and the newly cropped up Kashmir dispute; it hastily accepted the hand of friendship when offered by the United States.

The United States initially accepted legal validity of the accession of Kashmir to India. The American officials, however, in a meeting with their British counterparts on 27th February 1948 admitted that they knew very little about issue (Palit, 2001). In the next week on 4th March 1948, US Secretary of State General George C. Marshall sent a telegram to its embassy in India reiterating this point by observing that:

The Security Council cannot impose a settlement under chapter IV of the UN Charter but only make recommendations to the parties. Such recommendations must be made in the light of present jurisdiction of India over Kashmir, which makes complete civil and military neutralization (Joshi, 2019).

On 1st January 1949, ceasefire was made between the two countries, and it was agreed that the future of Kashmir would be decided as per the

UN resolutions. In 1950s, the United States worked closely with the various United Nations officials for the settlement of the Kashmir dispute. It faced an added pressure from Pakistan to go an extra mile since the later had very friendly ties with it. But even then, there were limits to which the United States was willing to go to oblige its enthusiastic ally. A memo of conversation between United States Secretary for States John Foster Dulles and Pakistan Prime Minister Malik Feroze Khan Noon (1957- 1958), in November 1957, indicates that Pakistan obsession got tiring for the United States. In 1959, United States signed a bilateral defense pact with Pakistan committing itself to defend Pakistan against any aggression from the communist Russia. In 1961, John Kennedy (1961-1963) took over the office of the president of the United States. He was a great admirer of Nehru's leadership and as a Congressman as well as a Senator had been a strong advocate of better ties with India.⁴¹ Kennedy Government's liking for India, at the cost of Pakistan, became exposed during the Indo-Chinese War of 1962 when it promptly put all its weight behind India and forced Pakistan not to take any benefit of the situation (M. A. Khan, 1967).

President Kennedy believed that a strong India was important for a free and politically stable Asia. However, he was equally mindful of the fact that so long as the Kashmir dispute remained unresolved, the Indian Subcontinent was vulnerable to exogenous influences leading to a highly fragile equilibrium in the regional balance of power. This sense of realization forced the United States Secretary of States Dean Rusk to visit India in 1963. He left Lidia to realize the complication of Kashmir issue and penned a gloomy assessment on the prospects of an early settlement. Back home, President Kennedy also fully knew that India and Pakistan regarded the Kashmir dispute as "more important than the struggle against communists" (Joshi, 2019).

The conflicting perceptions on Kashmir were aired again at the meeting of the UNSC in February 1962 when Pakistan raised the issue of the future of the State. India responded by

claiming to have an exclusive right on the whole of the State of Jammu and Kashmir. The US refrained from making negotiated settlement to Kashmir a precondition for continuing military assistance to Pakistan despite noticeable congressional pressure to act otherwise.

The United States military aid to India further augmented the defense capabilities of Delhi that had already been one of the biggest purchasers of the Russian arms. In fact, this was the time around when both the superpowers were eager to sell their arms to India since they wanted to reduce each other's "market share". This provided India a maneuvering space against the US pressure, which wanted to use the aid as an advantage against India over the Kashmir dispute. To make matters worse, Moscow meanwhile went overboard and strongly backed Indian position on Kashmir in the UN. Thus, rather than forcing India to agree to a peaceful settlement of the Kashmir conflict it got involved into a competition with Moscow to win over India to its side. Shrewd enough to realize the situation, India gave up any pretense of willingness to compromise on Kashmir

During the Ayub Khan regime (1958-1969), Pakistan made all possible efforts to normalize relation with India and to settle all the outstanding issues. Ayub Khan even went to the extent of proposing a joint defense agreement with India in March 1959 provided the Kashmir dispute was settled.⁵³ India flatly rejected this proposal as Prime Minister Nehru remarked, "I do not understand against whom people talk about common defense policy".⁵⁶

India, thus, completely backed out of the promise to settle the dispute as per the UN resolutions on the pretext that Pakistan was receiving military aid from the United States, which had disturbed the power balance in the region. Ironically speaking, this was the time around when India was also receiving economic and military aid from the United States. The major opinion in this UNSC meeting was in favor of a plebiscite. US, China and UK all supported plebiscite in the State while India and USSR opposed it. On 20 October 1962, Chinese forces launched a major attack on

Indian troops on the Thagla Ridge in the North East Frontier Agency. Attacks were also launched in areas claimed by Chinese in Ladakh which is a part of the State of Jammu and Kashmir. The war ended in a humiliating defeat for the Indian army in the Northeastern sector. Seven days after the war began on 29 October; Nehru formally sought United States military assistance. A day before India formally sought arms aid from the United States; Kennedy sent a note to President Ayub Khan requesting him not to use conflict to seek advantage on Kashmir. Even before the conflict was over, it was clear to Pakistan, if not to the United States that India's predicament had created a major leverage for the United States and Pakistan on the Kashmir issue.⁵³This all finally ended on the failure of negotiations taking place between the two sides over Kashmir in 1962-63.

It is pertinent to mention here that Ayub Khan believed that Pakistan should get Kashmir resolution through the auspices of United States friendship rather than at the expense of that.³⁷ On the other hand, Kennedy administration did not take long to force Ayub to assure India that in time of crisis Pakistan will not intervene in Kashmir. In fact, the aim of Kennedy administration was not to alienate India but forge close relations with it.

Carl Kaysen, the Deputy Special Assistant for national security affairs told President Ayub Khan that:

We are now faced with necessity of making Pakistan realize that their alliance with United States had been immense value to them. They are obviously weaker power, and they have been able to maintain as strong a line on Kashmir as they have in part because of the existence of our support in the background.

Kaysen further added that US was moving to tell Pakistan that:

We are not able to support their demand for a settlement via plebiscite and that their best opportunity for settlement on terms something like ratification of the status quo may be passing from their grasp. This will be a difficult and painful process, but it is one we must push through.

In a letter dated 13th November 1962, Ambassador Galbraith put down in a personal letter to Kennedy:

Eventually but not too soon the Indians must be asked to propose meaningful negotiations on Kashmir. This should not, incidentally raise the question of a plebiscite an idea in which there is no longer any future. The only hope lies in having a full guarantee of the headwaters of the rivers. Each side should hold on to the mountain territory that it has and there should be some sort of shared responsibility for the valley.

This was the time when Anglo-American countries tried to settle Kashmir dispute outside the United Nations framework. This effort was backed by Philip Talbot, the United States Assistant Secretary of State for Near East and South Asian Affairs in Washington and the National Security Council staffers Bob Komer and Carl Kaysen. But at every stage the President himself was involved. In Rawalpindi, Harriman and Sandys called on President Ayub Khan and the ensuing discussion focused on a draft of bilateral negotiation between two countries India and Pakistan. Harriman at this point sent a telegram to the headquarter that it would be impossible to have a plebiscite, that the vale as such could not be transferred to Pakistan, but that there was a understanding in India that they had to make certain concern beyond the present ceasefire line (Palit, 2001).

In 1963, Kashmir shot sharply into international focus with the disappearance of a sacred Islamic relic, a hair of the Prophet Mohammad (PBUH), from Hazrat Bal shrine. It created disturbance in Kashmir valley and Pakistan brought up this issue at the UNSC. The tension continued unabated, culminating in the outbreak of a war between the two sides. The United States at that time was badly engaged in Vietnam and was not able to manage things with ease. Security Council intervened in the situation and demanded that:

Ceasefire should take effect on Wednesday, Sep 22, 1965 at 700 hours GMT and calls upon both governments to issue orders for a ceasefire at that moment and the subsequent withdrawal of all armed personal back to position held by them

before August 5, 1965 (Manoj, 1999).

In March 1965, the Indian Legislative Assembly passed the "Integration Bill" giving Kashmir the status of a province of the union. This integration bill and imprisonment of Sheikh Abdullah sparked off the uprising in the early days of August. Government of India charged Pakistan of sending infiltrators into Kashmir. India finally crossed the borders of Pakistan and occupied Kargil post on 15th August 1965. It also attacked areas constituting Azad Kashmir. On 23rd September 1965, UNSC concluded a ceasefire between the two states.

Badly engaged in Vietnam, the US did not intervene in the conflict leaving ground for Russia to invite both parties to meet and discuss the differences and problems of the war on its soil. Both the parties accepted this invitation and consequently signed an agreement popularly known as 'Tashkent Declaration'. It also marked the triumph of Soviet Diplomacy. This declaration could not yield any real result since it provided no mechanism for solving the Kashmir dispute. The War of 1965 was a watershed in the history of American relations with the Indian Subcontinent. The United States alignment with Pakistan was to create a balance of power in the Subcontinent.

Secondly, United States massive economic support to India during late 50's and military aid after 1962 had been an indication to the point that the United States could cultivate friendly and productive relations with both countries. All these illusions were dashed to the ground in the wake of the war.

The United States also felt disenchanted by the unwillingness of India and Pakistan to stand by it in Vietnam (Farooq & Rashid, 2017). Consequently, it distanced itself from the Subcontinent as President Johnson directed the officials to adopt a low-profile policy vis-a-vis the Subcontinent and pursue a limited number of policy objectives. He further said that war had shaken the long held American policy assumption about the region. With this in the background, the United States did not take any interest in the agreement between India and Pakistan when signed while Soviet Union on the

other hand avoided help implement the agreement on ground.

In late 1960's, a movement broke out in the Eastern province of Pakistan primarily on the issue of language and politico-economic rights of the Bengalis resulting into a separate state of Bangladesh in 1971 (Bose, 2014). India did play a frontal role, both diplomatic and military, in the creation of this state and forced Islamabad for ceasefire on 17th December 1971.

During the War of 1971, India captured 93,000 Pakistani soldiers. Pakistan's President Zulfikar Ali Bhutto (1971-77) appealed to India to release the prisoners of war without linking it with other pending issues between the two sides. India agreed for negotiations on following conditions.

- Reorganize Bangladesh as an independent country.
- Settle the Kashmir conflict once and for all, around the exiting ceasefire line in Kashmir.

Pakistan major concern was the withdrawal of Indian troops from its territory and the release of its prisoners of war. In mid-February 1972, India changed its rigid stance and showed willingness to talk to Pakistan unconditionally.

On 28th June 1972, Bhutto and India Prime Minister Mrs. Indira Gandhi (1917-84), met for the first time and discussed the bilateral issues. On 2nd July 1972, the two states finally reached on Simla Agreement. During the parleys, India wanted to settle all issues simultaneously while Pakistan was more interested in immediate issues like releasing of the prisoners of war, disengagement of troops and the resumption of diplomatic relations. Pakistan rejected the Indian proposal to accept division of Kashmir on permanent basis and withdraw Kashmir dispute from the United Nations. It was, however, agreed that all outstanding issues/conflicts would be settled amicably and bilaterally. The acceptance of the principle of bilateralism was one of the major concessions that Mrs. Indira Gandhi won at Simla. India did not officially inform the UN about agreement and said, as a sensible body it should now to take the decision to abrogate the UN observer group arrangement. Pakistan's stance was

different; it argued that bilateralism did not bar the Kashmir issue in the United Nations. Bhutto declared in the National Assembly that he would not withdraw the issue from the United Nations. Such claims aside did not raise this issue in the Security Council until the end of Bhutto era.

In 1970, United States relations with India were at rock bottom. The was a committed military ally of Pakistan while India had very close and with the USSR with whom it had signed a friendship treaty in 1971 (Palit, 2001). In 1972, President Richard Nixon (1969-74) visited Beijing. In the joint communique issued by the two sides, Kashmir was declared a bilateral issue between India and Pakistan. In this context, Washington hailed the agreement India and Pakistan had reached in Simla. In this accord both countries pledged to solve the Kashmir and other problems bilaterally. They also undertook to respect the Line of Control (LoC) dividing their forces in the J&K State and to refrain from the threat of the use of force in violation of it (W. A. Khan, 2020). The agreement gave the United States an unassailable, thoroughly respectable rationale for remaining on the sidelines. Unable to change the situation in Kashmir, it was quite prepared to let the contestants work out the problem by themselves. If, as seemed likely at the time and for years afterward, they chose to put the issue in cold storage, that would be fine with Washington. Successive American administrations maintained this aloof position for the better part of two decades. Kashmir disappeared from the world's agenda and the Kashmiri people seemed to have become reconciled to their lot as Indian citizens.

The US military alliance with Pakistan and USSR with India had limited the scope of bilateral negotiations between the two contending sides. Under the new circumstances, the Subcontinent was facing new threats and challenges that included overt and covert nuclearization of India and Pakistan respectively. In 1977, United States passed a law (Glenn Symington Amendment) that called for termination of aid to any state involved in the import of uranium enrichment equipment or

technology. Pakistan became a soft victim of this law as it was alleged of importing this sort of technology from different countries (LaMontagne, 2001).

Soviet intervention into Afghanistan in 1979 marked an important event in the recent history of Subcontinent. The Soviet move was instrumental in reestablishing military ties between the United States and Pakistan that had weakened during the Bhutto years. It also played an important role to tailor the United States approach towards India and Kashmir.⁷⁰ Under the heat of the circumstances, the United States accorded Pakistan reasonable military and economic aid, which was around that time enhancing its covert nuclear program with Chinese assistance (Palit, 2001).

In 1981, United States suspended the sanctions applicable under the Glenn Symington Amendment with respect to Pakistan for a period of six years. The reason was the Soviet forces were still present in Afghanistan. The Region Administration justified greater military assistance to Pakistan on the ground that it would forward non-proliferation goals since an insecure Pakistan might look for nuclear option. Pakistan made best use of this opportunity to enhance its covert nuclear program. At different occasions, General Zia ul Haq (1977-88) casually raised the Kashmir issue in the United Nations but made no formal request for an intervention. History bears testimony to the fact that he was more concerned about the Russian threat from the Afghan side than long drawn Kashmir dispute. In brief, Pakistani efforts, no matter supporting bilateralism or United Nations involvement, could not produce the desired results. Worse, the United States also gave it a cold shoulder on the issue.

Uprising in Held Jammu and Kashmir

The outbreak of the Kashmir insurgency at the end of 1989 quickly returned Kashmir to Washington's radar screen. It feared that this time an India-Pakistan war could develop nuclear dimensions. It was also concerned with human rights violations by Indian forces. And it was troubled by the resistance fighters tactics

avored by some of the insurgent, especially those with Islamic credentials.

Despite these concerns, Washington declined to seek a mediating role. It stuck to the line that “the best way to resolve the Kashmir dispute is through direct discussions between the governments of India and Pakistan as envisaged in the Simla agreement.” After the uprising worsened, it added to this formulation, the point that in their bilateral discussions, the two governments should consider the wishes of the Kashmiri people. Washington did not offer advice about how this should be done.

The 1998 Indian and Pakistani nuclear tests greatly magnified Washington’s concerns about Kashmir. It now saw Kashmir as a nuclear “flashpoint”: that could ignite a nuclear war. It gave high priority to the resumption of the stalled India-Pakistan dialogue, including on Kashmir. But it continued to insist that it would not take a more direct role on Kashmir unless both sides agreed. Although the Pakistanis welcomed this internationalization of the dispute, a longtime Pakistani goal, the tests strengthened the primacy Washington gave to preserving stability in South Asia and lessened the importance it attached to the equities of the Kashmir issue. For Washington and other members of the international community, the use of violence to change the status quo was now not an acceptable option. Since it was essentially the status quo power, this approach favored India. President Clinton made the position clear when he pressured Pakistanis to withdraw their troops from the Kargil area of Indian Kashmir that they had seized in a military operation.

The Bush administration has tended to see the Kashmir issue primarily as a terrorist problem. This perspective is an outgrowth of September 11th and of the attack on the Indian parliament a few months later. So far, the administration has focused its efforts on persuading Pakistan government to terminate its support for cross-border terrorist activities. Its high-level interventions at critical moments in India-Pakistan tension have been designed primarily as fire-fighting operations. They have not dealt to

any extent with the basic problems in India-Pakistan relations, Kashmir foremost among them.

US Kashmir Policy during George Bush Era (1988-1991)

United States officials had never quite applied their minds to the Kashmir issue in two decades until the outbreak of massive resistance of 1989-90; US officials took a drift in their policies (Palit, 2001). At that time George W. Bush senior was in administration and before that Ronald Reagan was in power. During the time of 1982-87, Ronald Reagan’s sympathies were in favor of India and he improved his relations with India. Vice versa, Mrs. Gandhi and Rajeev Gandhi also tied up close relations with the United States. On the other hand, Pakistan was in crisis and facing sanctions from America. Pakistan did not raise the issue on the international level. US gave cold shoulders to Pakistan on the issue of Kashmir and asked India and Pakistan to solve their issues bilaterally. Pakistan highlighted this issue many times in the session of General Assembly, but no attention was paid.

Over the last four decades of the conflict, Kashmir had been a victim of the cold war between United States and Soviet Union as Pakistan was in the US block and India was in line with Soviet Union. Therefore, Moscow had persistently made every effort at the United Nations Security Council (UNSC) forum to block the settlement of the dispute according to the UN resolutions. Owing to Soviet veto, debate on Kashmir in the Security Council became futile exercise in mid 1950s.

The breakup of the Soviet Union marginalized Pakistan’s significance in the US power corridors. So, in the new world order Islamabad had lost its strategic partnership with Washington against communist forces in the region. Meanwhile, serious differences occurred on nuclear proliferation issue between the two countries. In fact, US tried its best to prevent Pakistan to become an atomic power from the very inception of its nuclear program. However, during joint campaign against Soviet aggression

in Afghanistan, US had to keep tight-lipped but with the Soviet force's withdrawal from Afghanistan in 1989, Pakistan's relationship with the US deteriorated sharply. Differences on nuclear program again surfaced. It was a real shock for Islamabad when the US administration imposed complete ban on military hardware sale and economic aid to Pakistan on 1st October 1990. United States administration refused to issue a certificate that had previously been certified. According to it "Pakistan did not have the nuclear bomb". This certificate was needed under the Pressler Amendment (Chakma, 2005).

Meanwhile, US gradually became a huge economic partner of India, Pakistan's archrival. While in the cold war era and particularly in the Afghan war, New Delhi appeared as main supporter of the Soviet Union and enthusiastically backed the Russian aggression. India did not even vote against Soviet invasion in the United Nations General Assembly, further reinforcing its image as a Soviet stooge. The breakup of the Soviet Union, freed US to focus on economic development and at that time Washington was desperately seeking new overseas markets for investments. With this new mindset, US quickly entered in a new phase of cooperation and trade relations with its old rivals such as Russia, India and even China in 1990. Indian government ignored the past allegiances and jumped into the American bandwagon. In the meantime, New Delhi abandoned its traditional anti-capitalist stance and adopted open market policy that was demanded by US. Moreover, Indian Prime Minister Narasimha Rao initiated revolutionary economic reforms, which also went well with Washington.

This new world scenario marginalized Islamabad's traditional international backing and support. In this changed global atmosphere, Kashmiris started mass movement and young generation took up arms against Indian rule in the disputed State of Jammu and Kashmir. Pakistan is a recognized party of the Kashmir dispute, and its people are emotionally attached with Kashmir's cause of "right of self-

determination" from day one. In this background, it was impossible for Islamabad to turn its back from Kashmir's struggle. The Government and civil society extended its full support to Kashmiri's resistance and still are committed to continuing it. This invited Indian anger and international brunt to some extent, particularly the United States. Gradually, US permanently adopted the role of "crisis management" in India Pakistan affairs with reference to Kashmir. This situation created a kind of triangle between India, Pakistan and US as "facilitator" or 'crisis manager' on the Kashmir issue. Following part of the paper deals the United States policies and strategies towards Kashmir conflict in this period.

Initial Phase of Uprising

It is a matter of fact that India had always been facing Kashmiri's resentment in different ways since early 1950s. Even pro-India leaders were also critical towards New Delhi's intention and conduct (Shah, 2018). The rigging of 1987's State elections became a turning point in the Kashmir history (Goldston, 1991). Kashmiri youth lost their confidence in the India political system and resorted to armed struggle in late 1989. Kashmiri masses also joined the youth and arranged popular protests (Joseph, 2000). Renowned human rights organization noted that "in one demonstration in late February, 1990, nearly 400, 000 Kashmiris...half the population of Srinagar—marched through the city to the office of the United Nation Military Observer Group to hand over petitions demanding independence" (Stylianou et al., 2015). New Delhi responded with iron hand and sent Mr. Jag Mohan as new governor on 18th January 1990 who declared *Governor's Rule* the very next day. Administration led by infamous Governor Jag Mohan handled the uprising with round-the-clock curfews and heavy handedness. Even peaceful protests were met with gunfire.

It was first occasion in the Kashmir history when Kashmiris emerged as a principal player of the conflict. Meanwhile, Kashmiri Diaspora especially residing in the United Kingdom and North America got involved in the struggle.

They formed their Kashmiri lobbying groups. Furthermore, Jammu and Kashmir Liberation Front (JKLF), purely nationalist outfit, led the Kashmiri struggle in early 1990s, which transformed traditional outlook of Kashmir as a territorial dispute between India and Pakistan, to a struggle for a Kashmiri self-rule and gave them a sense of pride. Therefore, international community saw this struggle indigenous, gave it media coverage, and to some extent illustrated with keen interest. The Indians came out with a charge sheet against Islamabad, alleged involvement in fueling the conflict rather to see the root cause of uprising. New Delhi took a host of measures to tackle mass resistance at various levels. Immediately, Indian Government imposed the *Governor Rule* and later on enacted draconian laws besides several others, including the Armed Forces (Jammu and Kashmir) Special Powers Act, 1990; Terrorist and Disruptive Activities Act (TADA), 1990; the Jammu & Kashmir Public Safety Act, 1978 (amended in 1990); and the Jammu & Kashmir Disturbed Areas Act, 1990. Rampant killing of innocent citizens became a regular feature those, which invited even more violence. This Indian strategy aggravated complete alienation and revenge in Kashmiri's mind and soul. In the meantime, India tried hard to get round the world that uprising in J&K State is part of global terrorism and fundamentalism wave.

It is understood that Islamabad has always had very deep interest in the internal dynamics of Kashmir. It is a matter of fact that on this occasion Islamabad could not properly guess the level of Kashmiris apathy towards Indian rule in Kashmir State. However, when Kashmiri people started struggle for their right of self-determination, it was almost impossible for Islamabad to turn its back towards Kashmiris in the time of need. Nevertheless, Pakistan was committed with Kashmir cause for a long time, hi this perspective, Islamabad extended full support to the resistance struggle. Besides this, the Pakistani people, media and the civil society got involved in the Kashmir issue and started supporting the resistance through different

ways.

Role of Pakistan in Movement

Dennis Kux commented in his book "Disenchanted Allies" about the role of Pakistan in the Kashmir Movement as:

Although Pakistan did not start the uprising in the Kashmir, the temptation to flame was too great for Islamabad to resist (Stylianou et al., 2015).

It was impossible for Pakistan to provide active backing to the Kashmiri freedom fighters. The support, supply and training system which was applied in Afghanistan was directed towards Kashmir. Quite apart from providing a means to support self-determination for Kashmiris long at the core of Pakistan's foreign policy. Helping the insurgency was also regarded as a fit way to pay India back for its support of the East Pakistan separation movement and the dismemberment of Pakistan in 1971. New Delhi strengthened its security forces in Kashmir and blamed Pakistan for the troubles. India continued to build up its military and paramilitary presence; artillery and mortar exchanges become more frequent and intense across the previously quiet LoC, the De-facto but porous frontier separating the Indian and Pakistani parts of Kashmir. VP Singh, who had defeated Rajeev Gandhi in the 1989 elections, raised the temperature further by publicly speaking of the possibility of an India Pakistan war.

VP Singh said on the 10th April 1990, that Pakistan has to pay the price, so war clouds were spreading over Pakistani and Indian borders (Kux, 2001). In New Delhi / Islamabad, Ambassador William Clark and Robert Oakley became concerned about the possibility of a conflict between two neighbors. They believed that both India and Pakistan have reached at the point where they might have nuclear weapons.

Initial US Response

In the early 1990s Kashmir issue had become a flashpoint in the international arena. Indian government led by VP Singh was almost daily issuing threats to Pakistan while inside Kashmir, people took their struggle to a maximum peak.

In this context, it was very important for international community and particularly for United States to position itself clearly on the newly emerged conflict in the heart of South Asia, Jammu and Kashmir. As earlier mentioned, in the first two decades of the conflict US was involved to settle this dispute at different levels including United Nations Security Council (UNSC) and at bilateral levels. Thus, it was not possible for the US to simply ignore the problem.

US Assistant Secretary of State for Near East and South Asia, John H. Kelly made a testimony before Asia-Pacific sub-committee of the House of Representatives and International Relations Committee on 6th March 1990 stating that "United State considers Jammu and Kashmir a disputed territory and urges both countries to settle it according to the Simla Agreement" (Stylianou et al., 2015). Subsequently, US Ambassador to Pakistan, Robert Oakley asked both countries to 'take into account the needs of the people of Kashmir' (Stylianou et al., 2015). This issue must be resolved between the Governments of India and Pakistan, as agreed at Simla in 1972, and take into account the needs of the people of Kashmir. We do not accept the Indian claim that Kashmir is part of India, and we have repeatedly expressed our concern over human rights abuses by Indian security forces. US does not accept India's claim on Kashmir: it was the first time when US emphasized to consider the wishes of Kashmiri people. This pronouncement gave hype to Kashmiri's expectations.

Indo-Pakistan Crisis of 1990

While international community and USA were in the phase of policy formulation on Kashmir, New Delhi brought its forces along the Pakistan borders. The two South Asian neighbors were at the brink of war in the spring of 1990 because of growing tensions over Kashmir. India moved more troops into the J&K to prevent allegedly cross-border infiltration from Pakistan and to intimidate hot pursuit or raids on 'training camps' in Pakistani territory. In the meantime, some US intelligence analysts were talking of a

possible nuclear exchange (Kux, 2001). As there was plenty of heightened rhetoric even the person not less than Prime Minister VP Singh lashed out at Pakistan in Indian Parliament on 10th April 1990, warning that it would have to pay a heavy price for its activities (Joshi, 2019). Likewise few weeks earlier Benazir Bhutto, Prime Minister of Pakistan, traveled to Muzaffarabad, capital of Azad Kashmir, and promised a "thousand-years' war" to support the resistance struggle (Mehta, 2019).

Under these circumstances Pakistan implicitly threatened to use nuclear weapons if India intervened militarily, across the LoC and, therefore, persuaded the US to act as an intermediary (Ahmed, 2004). The chronic conventional arms firing across the LoC in Kashmir increased manifold. In the light of growing risks of war between the two states and the likelihood that nuclear weapons might be used, the first Bush administration sent its national security adviser Robert M. Gates to Islamabad and New Delhi respectively, to lower the tension in the region (Ali, 2009). Beside this, US Senator Alan Craristion also visited both capitals and warned them; War between India and Pakistan would be a catastrophe for the people of both the countries. It could conceivably lead to the use of nuclear weapons, and it would not resolve the Kashmir problem.

Linkages between Nuclear and Kashmir Issue

Paradoxically, India Pakistan near war situation set out the alarm bells in Washington and they decided to get round Islamabad to abandon its nuclear program and Kashmir specific mindset. As mentioned before, US had already imposed economic and military sanctions against Pakistan under the Pressler Amendment. Besides this US put enormous diplomatic pressure on Pakistan to stop its nuclear program. US ambassador to Islamabad said that 'Pakistan is committing suicide'(Kux, 2001). To pursue their non-proliferation agenda at times American official even ignored the normal diplomatic norms and behaved like masters not friends. On the other hand, the Indian Government was desperately trying to find out alternative sources of

economic and diplomatic backing after the demise of Soviet Union which was India's main trading partner and most reliable source of economic assistance and military equipment. When US turned its back towards Pakistan it gave the Indians a sort of satisfaction and they thought it a golden opportunity to build up new relationship with Washington. To diversify its economy, India had already adopted economic reforms program in early 1991. In this context Indian Chief of Army visited Washington in July 1991 and said that 'in the new era the interests of Indian and US have converged. (Mahmud, 2005). Above all, India also provided fuel to US air forces in Bombay during first Gulf War in January 1991 and supported all resolutions against Iraq on UN forms. Meanwhile, India and US started to share the 'so called' danger of Islam. India sensed the opportunity and initially presented Kashmiri resistance in the prism of Islamic extremism, fundamentalism and anti-America (Jaswal, 2024).

Unjustified American diplomatic and economic pressure on Pakistan proved counterproductive and Islamabad became more dependent on its nuclear capability for country's security (Bahl, 2007).²¹ Islamabad thought that only the nuclear power could save it from superior Indian conventional military might. And under the nuclear shield Pakistan can continue its support to the fellow Kashmiris. Above all, this US attitude emboldened the Indians not to accept any conflict resolution deal with Pakistan.

The Kashmir dispute could not be solved during the turmoil of the cold war because during this period, the two countries were divided into US and Soviet blocks. Before the collapse of the Soviet Union and in the environment of cold war, America was afraid of communism. Pakistan was strategically important in this regard. America decided to make close relations with Pakistan. After the end of the cold war, the situation was opposite. USSR had reached its end, and the US was no longer afraid of the communist bloc. Therefore, there was no need for such kind of diplomatic relations with Pakistan; foreign policy emerged with new mindsets. That was towards economic,

technological and social sector developments. Now India was more appropriate than Pakistan and resultantly, no more affiliations towards Kashmir issue.

Conclusion

The former princely State of Jammu and Kashmir has been the primary cause of conflict between India and Pakistan since 1947. The two states have fought three wars over the Kashmir dispute. Historically speaking, the State got divided between the two countries following the 1948 war and gradually became one of the most contentious issues in the world. Today, both sides look at the issue in an emotional rather than a rational and realistic manner. The conflict has made hostage peace and stability in the region. India claims that Kashmir is an integral part of it while Pakistan thinks quite otherwise.

It goes as an undisputed fact that the world superpowers have unfortunately never shown a real interest in the resolution of this problem. Even the United Nations is still unable to find out a way to resolve the issue on a permanent basis. On the other hand, the initiatives taken by the US regarding Kashmir were not aimed at the peaceful and amicable settlement of this issue but to forward its different interests in the region either by aligning with Pakistan or India at different points in time.

The rivalry between the superpowers has also been a major hindrance in the settlement of Kashmir issue. The excessive use of veto by Soviet Union against Pakistan on the Kashmir issue in 1957 and then in 1962 badly harmed the cause of Kashmiris. To some quarters, it was Soviet retaliation to Pakistan for joining the US-led defense pacts. On the other hand, US aid and diplomatic support to Pakistan was never meant to force India to resolve Kashmir problem but to withhold the territorial expansion of communist Russia. In the same vein, it extended support to India to create a bulwark against Chinese's power and influence in the south Asian region. Kashmir unfortunately figured

nowhere in this equation.

Overall, Washington's Kashmir policy has not been consistent or strategically oriented during the decades. Instead of being principled or morally based, the United States has always shied away from making any categorical moral judgment of the conflict. This indecision is a mirror of a general trend of elevating geopolitical priorities above normative obligations. The same was the case with the

Soviet Union's policy, which also shied away from direct engagement or moral assessment. For the United States, its policy has been fashioned and refashioned by changing national interests—ranging from Cold War alignments, regional stability, and non-proliferation issues to counterterrorism and strategic alliances. Consequently, Washington's involvement in the Kashmir conflict has been generally reactive and opportunistic, not proactive or principled.

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